

“Presentation Prescription How B1+ Med Students Prepare for Oral Presentations in English”

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Abstract: Effective oral presentations are essential in Medical English and English for Specific Purposes (ESP), and understanding how students prepare can inform targeted pedagogy. In a broader cohort of 180 B1+ medical students, short post-presentation questionnaires were collected; of these, a purposive subsample of 42 students participated in semi-structured interviews, which were transcribed and thematically coded for this paper. The interview data capture step-by-step preparation practices and resource choices (e.g., slide templates, online/bilingual dictionaries, ChatGPT, Canva), as well as affective responses to presenting in English. Thematic analysis reveals predominant use of slide templates and online reference resources, a high rate of AI-assisted presentation preparation, and pervasive presentation anxiety. These findings highlight the interplay of learner autonomy, digital literacy, and cognitive load, and point to concrete curricular interventions (e.g., AI tool training and design guidance) for ESP courses.

Keywords: ESP; Medical English; presentation skills; learner autonomy; AI-assisted learning; digital tools; thematic analysis

Literature review:

Although the use of generative AI in education has recently attracted substantial scholarly attention, most existing research focuses on writing assistance, automated feedback, or general attitudes toward tools such as ChatGPT. Few studies explore how students actually prepare for oral presentations, particularly in the context of English for Specific Purposes. Abdelhafiz et al. (2025), for instance, conducted a large-scale survey among medical students in Egypt, examining awareness and general use of ChatGPT in learning activities. However, that work did not investigate the broader process of presentation preparation or the combination of multiple tools. In contrast, the present study draws on interview data to trace how medical students plan and construct their presentations in English—whether or not they use AI assistance. To our knowledge, no prior research has examined this topic within medical ESP, and none within the Bulgarian context, which highlights both the novelty and the practical relevance of the present investigation.

Methods:

This study analysed a purposive subsample of 42 interviews drawn from a larger cohort of 180 B1+ medical students who participated in their end-of-year speaking exam. Purposive sampling was chosen in order to capture diversity in students’ preparation strategies, with attention to differences between those who used AI tools and those who did not, between template users and non-users, and across varying self-reported anxiety levels. Such an approach ensures information-rich cases are included while aligning the dataset with the overall aims of the research (Campbell et al., 2020). Interviews were conducted immediately after each student delivered a short oral presentation, a timing that was intended to reduce retrospective distortion and capture preparation practices while they remained salient.

All interviews were audio-recorded with informed consent and subsequently transcribed verbatim. Transcription employed a hybrid workflow: initial drafts were generated using an intelligent speech-recognition system and then manually corrected against the original audio. This

method balances efficiency with accuracy, reduces transcription time, and helps address the known limitations of automated systems, such as bias or error in domain-specific vocabulary (Eftekhari et al., 2024; McMullin et al., 2021). Final transcripts were anonymized by removing or pseudonymizing all identifying details. Data were stored securely on institutional systems in accordance with ethical guidelines.

Analysis followed an inductive thematic approach, identifying patterns in participants' accounts rather than imposing pre-existing theoretical categories. The research team drew on Braun and Clarke's (2021) six-phase framework for reflexive thematic analysis, moving from familiarisation and coding to generating, refining, and defining themes, before preparing the analytic narrative. The approach remained flexible and interpretive, aiming to prioritise the voices of participants while acknowledging the active role of the researchers in meaning-making (Byrne, 2022).

Rather than using specialised qualitative analysis software, the team managed and coded the data through a structured Microsoft Excel workbook. Each transcript was segmented into analyzable units, which were then entered into a table alongside participant ID, segment text, and researcher-edited extracts where necessary. Additional columns included broad codes, subcodes, binary indicators (e.g., AI use, template adoption, self-reported anxiety), source tags (Google, Wikipedia, YouTube), and analytic memos. This spreadsheet-based method facilitated both transparency and auditability, while also allowing the use of pivot tables and filters to group codes, identify patterns, and generate descriptive counts of behaviours (Clarke, 2021).

Coding was conducted iteratively and reflexively. Two researchers independently coded the transcripts, working inductively to generate codes that captured the diversity of preparation practices, while also flagging mentions of specific tools or resources such as ChatGPT, SlidesGo, or online dictionaries. A subset of transcripts was double-coded, and differences were discussed to enhance interpretive depth rather than to enforce mechanical agreement. This process aligns with contemporary debates that emphasise the value of reflexive dialogue over rigid intercoder reliability metrics (O'Connor & Joffe, 2020). Where disagreements persisted, alternative interpretations were recorded in memos before consensus decisions were made.

Once coding was complete, related codes were grouped into higher-order themes, and illustrative anonymised quotations were selected. Descriptive statistics were also generated from the binary indicators in the Excel sheet. This enabled the team to report, for example, how many participants mentioned using AI, templates, or specific online resources. While these counts were not treated as inferential data, they provided useful context for understanding the prevalence of practices discussed in qualitative themes. Such integration of qualitative themes with descriptive numerical summaries reflects current pragmatic mixed-methods practice, which seeks to enhance rigour and credibility through methodological complementarity (Fetters et al., 2013; Lorenzini, 2024).

Throughout the process, reflexivity was central. Coding was understood as interpretive and situated, with transparency achieved by documenting decisions in the Excel file and through memo writing. Although Excel does not offer all the functionalities of dedicated qualitative analysis software, its use in small- to medium-sized projects has been validated as a practical, transparent, and auditable solution (Clarke, 2021). Ethical considerations were prioritised at every stage. All

participation was voluntary, informed consent was obtained, and strict anonymisation and secure storage procedures were applied to protect student privacy (Newman, 2021; McMullin et al., 2021).

This combination of reflexive thematic analysis with an Excel-based coding workflow allowed the study to capture nuanced accounts of how medical students prepared for oral presentations while also providing descriptive indicators of the frequency of particular practices. The approach balances depth with transparency and contributes to methodological discussions about adapting thematic analysis for contemporary classroom-based ESP research (Braun & Clarke, 2021; Byrne, 2022).

Results

Forty-two semi-structured interviews were transcribed and coded for this analysis; counts below refer to that coded subsample (see Methods for sampling details). Table 1 summarizes tool use and source choices reported by participants, and the paragraphs that follow synthesize the quantitative counts with the qualitative themes emerging from the interviews.

Item	n	%
Any AI assistant	31	73.8%
— ChatGPT 4.0	30	71.4%
— Gemini	1	2.4%
Used a slide/template	23	54.8%
— SlidesGo	9	21.4%
— Canva	3	7.1%
— Downloaded template (other)	11	26.2%
Used Google to find information	15	35.7%
Used YouTube as a source	4	9.5%
Used Wikipedia as a source	8	19.0%
Used a dictionary/translator	13	31.0%
Reported feeling anxious about presenting	32	76.2%

Table 1. Reported resources and affect ($N = 42$)

Quantitatively, the most widely reported preparatory resource was an AI assistant: 31 of 42 participants (73.8%) reported using some form of AI, overwhelmingly ChatGPT 4.0 (30/42, 71.4%), with only a single mention of Gemini. Slide-based preparation was also common: slightly more than half the sample (23/42, 54.8%) used a slide template; named template sources included SlidesGo (9/42, 21.4%) and Canva (3/42, 7.1%), and a further 11 students (26.2%) reported downloading a template from another site. For factual content and terminology students most often reported search engines and online references: Google was used by 15 students (35.7%), Wikipedia by 8 students (19.0%), and YouTube by 4 students (9.5%). Dictionaries or translators (online or bilingual) were reported by 13 students (31.0%).

Qualitative analysis elaborated why and how these resources were used. AI assistants were primarily used for structural support and drafting: students typically described asking the assistant for outlines, slide sequences, or phrasing suggestions and then editing the output for accuracy and personal voice. Template use reflected a clear separation of content and design work: many students reported relying on ready-made slide structures to organize content quickly and to produce a visually acceptable product without in-depth design work. Google and Wikipedia were commonly used to locate definitions, clinical descriptions or images, whereas YouTube was cited mainly for finding explanatory videos or graphical resources.

Presentation anxiety was prevalent: 32 participants (76.2%) reported feeling anxious about their presentations. The interviews reveal two overlapping sources of anxiety. The first is language-specific worry: many students explicitly linked heightened nerves to presenting in English (for example, “I’m afraid because it’s in English” or “I understand the text, but I can’t speak English confidently”), indicating concern about fluency, vocabulary retrieval, and pronunciation. The second is more general public-speaking anxiety that would occur irrespective of language: several students said they would feel nervous presenting in Bulgarian as well, pointing to trait-level discomfort with public performance. Students’ affective reports included hyperbolic numeric expressions (e.g., “11 out of 10”), which were treated in analysis as qualitative indicators of very high distress rather than as precise measures.

Rehearsal strategies varied across participants. Many described self-practice (silently or aloud) and last-minute checks, a subset reported practicing with peers or family for feedback, and a few described deliberately limiting the amount of text on slides to reduce memorization load. Where students used AI or online sources to draft content, they commonly combined these with personal editing and rehearsal to ensure they could deliver the material in their own words.

In sum, the coded interviews portray a cohort that frequently leverages digital tools—most notably ChatGPT and slide templates—to scaffold presentation creation, while continuing to depend on search engines and dictionaries for factual and lexical support. At the same time, high levels of presentation anxiety, stemming from both language concerns and general public-speaking apprehension, persist and shape how students prepare (for example, favouring templates to reduce cognitive load or rehearsing aloud to compensate for lexical uncertainty). These quantitative counts and thematic observations form the empirical basis for the discussion and pedagogical recommendations that follow.

Discussion

The findings indicate that digital tools—especially large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT—and slide templates have become central to how B1+ medical students prepare oral presentations. Most students in the coded subsample reported using AI to draft or structure content, while slightly more than half relied on slide templates to organise material and manage the visual design. These behaviours appear to reflect pragmatic attempts to reduce cognitive load: students outsource initial structuring to AI and pre-designed slides so they can focus rehearsal efforts on delivery and lexical retrieval. At the same time, students continue to use traditional reference resources (search engines, dictionaries, Wikipedia) to check facts and domain terms, indicating a hybrid workflow in which generative and referential tools coexist.

The predominance of AI use raises pedagogical and epistemic questions. On the one hand, AI-assisted drafting can scaffold novices' macro-organization and lower barriers to starting a presentation; on the other hand, it creates new demands for verification, adaptation, and voice authenticity. Our qualitative data show that students typically edited AI output, which suggests some level of critical engagement, but self-report cannot reveal how deeply they checked factual claims, medical terminology, or phrasing appropriateness. This ambiguity has implications for both assessment and instruction: instructors must teach not only how to use LLMs productively (prompting, editing, verification) but also how to evaluate and attribute AI-generated material responsibly.

Affectively, presentation anxiety was widespread and multifaceted. Many students explicitly attributed much of their anxiety to performing in English—concerns about fluency, word retrieval and pronunciation—while others described a more general discomfort with public speaking that would appear regardless of language. These emotional responses interact with tool choice: for some learners, templates and AI-supported outlines were adopted as coping mechanisms to reduce memorization and to create a predictable structure; for others, heavy reliance on external scaffolds may reflect avoidance of the linguistic challenge rather than a step toward greater independence. Designing classroom opportunities that scaffold graded exposure to public speaking and that combine language-focused rehearsal with tool-mediated drafting may therefore help reduce anxiety while building competence.

An important, candid observation from the research process bears emphasising. While it is unsurprising that students want to engage with new technologies, we explicitly encouraged honesty during interviews because the extent to which learners are using and trusting modern LLMs is not always obvious to instructors. From the interviews it is reasonable—perhaps blunt—to say that LLMs have rapidly embedded themselves into students' practices; in the words of one researcher on the project, they have “infested in our students' ear and nesting.” How persistent this embedding will be, and what long-term effects it will have on skills such as spontaneous lexical retrieval, critical appraisal, and academic integrity, remains an open question that requires longitudinal investigation.

Several limitations temper interpretation of these results. The analysis is based on a purposive subsample of 42 interviews drawn from a cohort of 180, and findings rely on self-report rather than direct observation of preparatory workflows; social desirability or recall bias may therefore influence what students disclosed. The interview protocol's practice of omitting questions already answered reduced repetition but may have limited the comparability of responses across participants. Finally, our coding captured whether tools were used but not the intensity, timing, or exact nature of use (for example, whether AI produced final phrasing or only an initial outline); mixed-method approaches that combine self-report with artifact analysis (version histories, prompts, draft comparisons) would provide a more granular picture.

For practice and future research, several concrete steps follow. Instructors should incorporate short, practical modules on responsible and effective AI use—how to craft useful prompts, how to verify model outputs against authoritative sources, and how to adapt AI suggestions so that final speech reflects the student's voice. Teaching slide-design heuristics alongside template-selection strategies could reduce unnecessary cognitive load and encourage better visual communication. Assessment policies should be clarified so students understand

expectations around authorship, attribution and acceptable levels of AI assistance. Methodologically, future work should track preparatory workflows longitudinally, examine correlations between extent of AI reliance and oral performance outcomes, and explore interventions (e.g., scaffolded AI-free rehearsal phases) to test causal effects on learning and anxiety.

In conclusion, our study shows that students are already using a mix of generative and referential digital tools to prepare presentations in medical English, and that these tools shape both the mechanics of preparation and the emotional experience of presenting. The pedagogy of ESP must adapt: embracing the affordances of new technologies while actively teaching the critical literacies required to use them well. The precise trajectory of LLM integration into student practice—how deep, how long, and with what consequences—remains to be determined, but it is clear that educators should act now to guide that integration constructively.

Conclusion

This study of 42 transcribed interviews from a cohort of 180 B1+ medical students shows that digital tools — particularly large language models (predominantly ChatGPT) and slide templates — are now central to how students prepare oral presentations in English. Students commonly combine AI-generated structure with online reference checks and templates to manage cognitive load, while rehearsal practices and affective responses vary widely. Presentation anxiety remains high and stems from both language-specific concerns and more general public-speaking apprehension; in many cases students adopt tools and templates as pragmatic coping strategies.

Pedagogically, these findings call for immediate, practical responses: integrate short modules on responsible and effective LLM use (prompting, verification, adaptation, and attribution), teach simple slide-design and template-adaptation heuristics to reduce extraneous cognitive load, and provide scaffolded rehearsal opportunities that gradually increase public-speaking demands. Assessment policies should be clarified so students understand acceptable forms and limits of AI assistance.

Finally, while students' eagerness to engage with new technologies is understandable, the rapid and deep uptake of LLMs—already embedded in student practice—raises open questions about long-term effects on language development, critical appraisal, and academic integrity. Longitudinal and artifact-based studies are needed to trace how persistent and influential this integration will be. Meanwhile, educators should act proactively to guide students toward critical, transparent, and pedagogically sound uses of these tools.

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